

Mapping Research Topics on Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) in Sharia and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and literature review. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the DER ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the DER ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the DER ratio using a literature review study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 69 journal publications regarding the DER ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the DER ratio are divided into 6 clusters and 196 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of literature review studies, there are 20 topics around the DER ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around DER ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Debt to Equity Ratio (DER), Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Islamic and Conventional Banking.

Introduction

The Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) is one of the most important financial ratios in the banking industry. This ratio is used to measure how much the bank's liabilities (debt) are compared to the bank's owner's capital (equity). The higher the DER ratio, the greater the amount of debt the bank has compared to the owner's capital. The use of the DER ratio in banking is becoming increasingly important as the banking industry becomes increasingly complex and regulatory supervision requirements become increasingly stringent. Banks today are increasingly paying attention to their financial health and managing risks better. The DER ratio is one of the indicators most often used in evaluating a bank's financial health.

The DER ratio is also often used by the government and regulators as a tool for monitoring and evaluating bank financial health. Regulators usually set maximum DER ratio limits for banks operating in their countries to ensure that banks are not overburdened by debt and are able to repay their debts in a timely manner. However, it should be remembered that the use of the DER ratio in evaluating a bank's financial health cannot be seen separately from other factors such as asset quality, liquidity and profitability. Therefore, banks usually also use other financial ratios in evaluating their financial health. In recent years, the use of the DER ratio in the banking industry has also grown with the emergence of fintech which offers different banking products and services. Fintechs that offer online loans often use the DER ratio as a benchmark in evaluating borrower risk and determining loan eligibility. In conclusion, the use of the DER ratio in banking continues to grow along with the complexity of the banking industry and increasing regulatory supervision requirements. This ratio is an important indicator in evaluating a bank's financial health and determining the bank's ability to provide

loans to customers. However, the use of the DER ratio cannot be seen separately from other factors in evaluating a bank's financial health.

Research on the use of the DER ratio in banking continues to grow along with the increasing importance of this ratio in evaluating a bank's financial health and determining the bank's ability to provide loans to customers. Some interesting research developments regarding the use of DER ratios in banking include the following: first, research shows that banks with low DER ratios tend to have higher profitability. This shows that banks with a healthy capital structure tend to be better able to generate greater profits. Second, research shows that banks with high DER ratios tend to have higher credit risk. This shows that a poor capital structure can increase bank credit risk. Third, research shows that large companies tend to have lower DER ratios compared to small companies. This shows that large companies tend to have access to more capital, so they do not need to rely on debt to finance their operations. Fourth, research shows that strict regulations on the use of debt can affect bank capital structure. Strict regulations can encourage banks to use owner's capital as the main source of funding, thereby increasing the equity ratio and reducing the DER ratio. Overall, research on the use of the DER ratio in banking continues to grow along with the increasing importance of this ratio in evaluating the financial health of banks. This research helps regulators, banks and investors to understand the influence of the DER ratio on banking financial performance and determine appropriate strategies to improve bank financial health.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding DER in Sharia and Conventional Banking by using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature developments in publications in a scientific field by creating metadata network maps; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding DER. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research DER. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics surrounding the DER ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Literature Review

Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) or Debt to Equity Ratio is a financial ratio used to measure how much debt a company has compared to the amount of equity or own capital the company has. In the banking context, DER is used to measure how much liabilities or debt a bank has compared to its capital. The higher the DER of a bank, the greater the proportion of debt or liabilities the bank has compared to its capital. DER is usually calculated by dividing total debt (including long-term debt and current debt) by the bank's total equity or own capital. If the result is greater than one, it means the bank has more debt than its capital, whereas if the result is less than one, it means the bank has more capital than its debt.

Bibliometric studies constitute Quantitative analysis method used to measure and analyze the characteristics of scientific publications in a particular discipline or research field. This method involves collecting and analyzing data taken from references or bibliography contained in scientific publications. Bibliometric studies can be used to study research trends, collaboration networks between researchers, citation patterns, and the impact of a scientific publication on a particular research field. Through bibliometric analysis, important information can be found about how often a scientific article is cited, which authors or journals have contributed the most to a field, and how the field has developed over time. Bibliometric studies generally involve the use of specialized software to collect and

analyze bibliographic data from relevant scientific publications. The data collected can be the number of publications, number of citations, or h-Index and g-Index from certain researchers or certain journals. Bibliometric studies are becoming increasingly important in today's research world, especially in continuously developing fields such as science and technology. This method can help researchers and research institutions in making strategic decisions about funding, research and development in the future.

VOSviewer is data analysis and visualization software used to perform bibliometric analysis and produce network maps from scientific articles, journals, or researchers in a particular field or research discipline. This software was developed by Prof. Nees Jan van Eck and Ludo Waltman from the Center for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS) at Leiden University, the Netherlands. VOSviewer can be used to visualize citation networks between articles, collaboration between authors or institutions, and density patterns of keywords in scientific publications. By combining various types of bibliometric data, VOSviewer can help researchers to understand more deeply about specific research areas, research trends, and the relationships between certain concepts or topics. One of the main features of VOSviewer is its ability to create interactive and easy-to-understand network maps, using different colors and sizes of nodes and links to show the relationships between those nodes. VOSviewer can also allow users to perform cluster analysis or multidimensional scaling (MDS) analysis on their bibliometric data. VOSviewer is free to use and can be downloaded from the official VOSviewer website. The software has a simple and easy-to-use interface, so it can be used by researchers or practitioners who do not have a specific background or experience in bibliometric analysis or data visualization.

Studies literature review is research methods used to review, analyze, and synthesize relevant literature or information sources in a particular research field or topic. Literature review studies aim to understand and identify weaknesses and strengths of previous research, provide a summary and holistic understanding of research developments in a field, and identify needs and opportunities for further research. Literature review studies can be carried out using various types of information sources, such as journal articles, books, official documents, and other sources of information. The analysis carried out in a literature review study includes data collection, filtering, assessment, and synthesis from information sources relevant to the topic or research question. Literature review studies are very important in research because they help the researcher to understand the current status of research in the chosen field. This can help researchers to develop more effective and efficient research, and can help identify research gaps that are still unanswered or require further research. Literature review studies can also help in developing a theoretical framework, determining an appropriate research design, and helping develop more specific hypotheses or research questions. In addition, literature review studies can help identify problems or difficulties in previous research, and strengthen previous research by adding newer and more relevant sources of information.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The research object is the Debt to Equity Ratio (DER). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on DER in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection comes from search for accredited national journals, Sinta via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software,

Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish / Harzing software, then search for journals by category title words with the keywords " Debt to Equity Ratio " and " DER" throughout the year; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding DER using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and journal publication trends around DER using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around DER using a literature review study.

Results and Discussion

Distribution of Scientific Publications regarding Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

There are 69 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Garba Reference Digital) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2009 to 2023. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal publication data about DER by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2009	2	2016	7	2020	10
2013	3	2017	5	2021	7
2014	2	2018	8	2022	19
2015	3	2019	3		

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

VOSviewer Bibliometric Study Mapping of Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Search results for articles on software Perish/Harzing are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

dependent variable, eps, equity and debt, financial statement data, idx, independent variable, list, multiple linear regression, net interest margin, npl, panel data regression, performing loan, Persero, price earning ratio, purposive sampling technique, quantitative approach, research method, sample method technique, service solution, significance level, significant influence, study, tbk.

- Cluster 5 consists of 18 topic items, namely: classic assumption test, coefficient, data collection method, determination coefficient, dividend payout ratio, dpr, equity ratio to profitability, f test, financial performance, banking companies, profit growth, ratio, spss program, t test, value.
- Cluster 6 consists of 18 topic items, namely: certain criteria, current ratio and debt, earnings per share, equity ratio, impact, level, multiple regression analysis, partial test, influence of current ratio, per, quantitative research, sample company, share, significant to share prices, stock price.

Mapping Literature Review Study regarding the Influence of Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) on Sharia and Conventional Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 20 influences of DER on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

First, bond rating. The influence of DER in banking on bond rating can vary depending on the level of DER and the overall financial condition of the bank. Generally, the higher a bank's DER, the greater the financial risk it has. This can affect the bond rating (rating) issued by the bank. Bond ratings are usually assigned by rating agencies such as Standard & Poor's, Moody's, and Fitch Ratings. This institution carries out financial analysis of banks and assesses the credit risk associated with bonds issued by banks. If a bank's DER is too high, the rating agency may judge that the bank has a high credit risk, and therefore, the bonds issued by the bank will have a lower rating. Conversely, if a bank's DER is relatively low, the rating agency may judge that the bank has low credit risk, and therefore, the bonds issued by the bank will have a higher rating.

Second, Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR). The effect of DER on CAR can vary depending on the company's situation and conditions. However, in general, the higher a company's DER, the lower its CAR. This is because the higher the DER, the greater the portion of the company's debt compared to its equity. This debt will then become an interest expense that must be paid by the company, thereby increasing operational costs and affecting the company's ability to meet CAR requirements. Banking has fairly high CAR requirements to ensure that companies can bear credit risk and operational risk. Therefore, banking companies must pay attention to their DER to ensure that they have healthy debt levels and can meet CAR requirements. If the DER is too high, banking companies may need to reduce their debt levels or increase their capital to meet CAR requirements. Conversely, if the DER is too low, banking companies may not utilize their leverage potential optimally.

Third, Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR). In banking, DER can influence the DPR. The higher the DER, the more loans the bank uses, causing the bank to have to pay higher interest. This can cause a decrease in bank net profit. Therefore, if a bank's DER is high, the bank may tend to limit dividend payments in order to reduce interest expenses and strengthen its financial position. However, the influence of DER on the DPR is not always negative. If the bank can utilize the loan well and get a return on investment that is higher than the cost of borrowing, then the bank can maintain or increase the DPR. In this case, DER can be used as a tool to increase shareholder investment returns through dividend payments.

Fourth, expected return. – The influence of DER on banking expected returns depends on the situation and market conditions. In general, the higher a bank's DER, the greater the bank's risk of bankruptcy. However, the greater the risk taken, the greater the potential for getting higher returns. In a stable market situation, banks with high DER tend to have higher expected returns compared to banks with low DER. However, in unstable market situations or experiencing a crisis, banks with high DER tend to have high expectations lower returns and greater risk of bankruptcy. In practice, banks tend to pursue optimal DER, namely DER that provides maximum profits with manageable risks. Therefore, the influence of DER on banking expected returns will vary depending on the market situation and the management strategy adopted by each bank.

Fifth, share prices. The effect of DER on banking share prices can vary depending on market conditions and other factors that influence the bank's financial performance. In some cases, investors may view a high DER as a sign that the bank is taking too much risk and may be less financially stable. This can reduce investor confidence and reduce share prices. However, in other cases, a high DER may be considered a sign that the bank has an opportunity to expand its business by utilizing loans. If the bank manages to generate sufficient profits to pay interest and repay debt, a high DER can be considered a positive factor and can increase share prices. In addition, the effect of DER on banking share prices can vary depending on overall market conditions. When the market is sluggish, investors may be more inclined to avoid banks with high DER because they are considered riskier. However, in a growing market, investors may be more inclined to buy bank shares with a high DER because they are perceived to have greater growth potential.

Sixth, hedging. DER is a ratio that measures how much debt a company uses compared to its own capital or company equity. DER is one of the factors that influences the implementation of hedging in banking. Basically, the higher a company's DER, the greater the financial risk it faces. In terms of banking, a high DER can result in higher liquidity risk, credit risk and market risk. Therefore, banks tend to be more active in implementing hedging strategies to reduce this risk. In this context, hedging can help banks to reduce risks associated with fluctuations in interest rates, foreign exchange rates and credit risk. In practice, banks can use various hedging instruments such as futures contracts, options, swaps, and so on to protect their portfolios from unexpected market fluctuations. However, implementing hedging also requires significant costs and resources. Therefore, banking companies need to carefully consider the use of hedging instruments, especially if their DER is already high. If the DER is too high, then banking companies may have difficulty obtaining new funds or even face the risk of bankruptcy if there is a decline in market value or a financial crisis. In conclusion, DER influences the implementation of hedging in banking. The higher a company's DER, the greater the financial risk it faces, so banks tend to be more active in implementing hedging strategies to reduce this risk. However, banking companies also need to carefully consider the use of hedging instruments, especially if their DER is already high.

Seventh, Islamic Social Reporting (ISR). In general, DER can influence ISR in two ways: (1) If companies have high DER, then they will rely more on debt financing. Because of this, they may focus more on repaying debt and generating enough profit to pay back their debt. This may impact a company's prioritization of social and environmental initiatives, which could become less of a priority. (2) On the other hand, companies with low DER tend to have more equity capital, which can be used to develop CSR and ISR programs. Because they are less burdened by interest payments or debt obligations, companies may be better able to prioritize their social responsibilities.

However, in the banking sector, the relationship between DER and ISR may be slightly different. Banks generally rely on large amounts of debt funding, and that's not a bad thing as long as they maintain the ability to repay that debt. Banks also have a very important social role, as they play an important role in facilitating economic growth and providing credit to people in need. As a result, in the case of banking, DER may not have a significant impact on ISR. Although banks have an obligation to repay their debts, they also have strong social and environmental responsibilities, which may encourage them to report their business practices transparently and make positive contributions to society and the environment. Therefore, in this case, DER does not have to be the main determining factor in banking ISR.

Eighth, investor confidence. In the banking sector, DER can have a significant influence on investor confidence. As financial institutions, banks take risks by providing loans and investments that have the potential to generate large profits, but also have a potentially detrimental risk of default. Investors will have more confidence in banks that have a healthy DER, namely a moderate and stable DER. A DER that is too high can indicate that the bank is taking on too much risk by borrowing too much, thereby increasing the likelihood of default. On the other hand, a DER that is too low can indicate that the bank is not maximizing the use of its own capital to expand its business, so it may be less competitive and unable to meet large credit demands. Therefore, investor confidence in banks can be influenced by DER. Banks with healthy DERs can demonstrate their ability to manage risk and generate stable profits, which can increase investor confidence. Conversely, banks with unhealthy DERs can raise concerns and reduce investor confidence, which can disrupt the bank's ability to obtain funding from the capital markets or access capital from investors.

Ninth, profit growth. In banking, DER can influence profit growth in several ways: (1) Influence on the cost of capital: a high DER indicates that the bank uses more debt than its own capital to finance its operations. In the short term, this can reduce the cost of capital because the interest paid on debt is lower than the cost of equity. However, in the long term, a high DER can increase the risk of bankruptcy because banks have an obligation to pay interest and principal on debt. These risks may increase long-term capital costs and may limit earnings growth. (2) Effect on liquidity: high DER can also affect banking liquidity because debt must be repaid within a certain period, whereas capital itself does not require repayment. If banks are unable to repay their debts, their liquidity could be affected, which in turn could affect profit growth. (3) Influence on availability of funds: High DER can also affect the availability of banking funds. If banks have difficulty paying their debts, investors and creditors can withdraw their funds, which can reduce the availability of funds for banks. This can limit banks' ability to make investments and can affect profit growth.

Tenth, Net Interest Margin (NIM). In banking, DER can affect NIM because the higher the DER, the more debt the company must pay off. This can cause the company to have to pay higher interest, thereby reducing NIM. In addition, the higher the DER, the greater the financial risk faced by the company. This risk can cause companies to have to set larger reserves to protect themselves from credit risk, which can ultimately lead to a reduction in NIM. However, on the other hand, DER that is too low can also affect NIM. Banking companies that have DERs that are too low may have limited access to funding sources, which in turn can limit business growth and reduce NIM. Therefore, optimal DER must be considered to minimize risk and maximize NIM.

Eleventh, company value. The effect of DER on company value can vary depending on the situation and conditions of the company. However, in general, a DER that is too high can result in greater interest expenses and a higher risk of

bankruptcy. On the other hand, a DER that is too low can indicate that the company is not maximizing the use of debt to expand its business and can hinder the company's growth. In the banking context, a balanced DER can help increase company value by maximizing the use of debt and own capital. However, if the DER is too high, the company may face a higher risk of bankruptcy and a significant decline in financial performance.

Twelfth, Murabahah financing. The influence of DER on murabahah financing (a financing system based on the principle of buying and selling with a markup) in banking can be seen from two points of view: (1) Banking point of view: a high DER can be an indication that a bank has a large debt burden and significant financial risk. This can cause banks to have difficulty fulfilling their debt payment obligations and cause a decline in investor confidence in these banks. Conversely, a low DER indicates that banks have sufficient capital to finance their operations. This can increase investor confidence and banking credibility, making it easier for banks to obtain sources of murabahah financing. (2) Customer perspective: A low DER can provide a sense of security for customers in obtaining murabahah financing from banks. This is because banks have lower financial risk and tend to have lower interest rates. On the other hand, a high DER can make customers hesitate to obtain murabahah financing from banks because banking financial risks are high and interest rates tend to be higher. In conclusion, DER can influence murabahah financing in banking. A low DER can increase banking credibility and provide a sense of security for customers in obtaining murabahah financing. Therefore, banks need to pay attention to DER to ensure business continuity and increase customer and investor confidence.

Thirteenth, Price to Book Value (PBV). In the banking context, DER has a significant influence on PBV. Banks that have a high DER tend to have a low PBV, because a high DER indicates that the bank has a greater level of debt compared to its own capital. This means that the bank has a higher risk, so investors tend to give a lower PBV value. On the other hand, banks that have a low DER tend to have a higher PBV, because a low DER indicates that the bank has a lower level of debt compared to its own capital. This means that the bank has lower risk, so investors tend to give a higher PBV value.

Fourteenth, Price Earning Ratio (PER). The effect of DER on PER in banking can vary depending on various factors. Some possible effects are as follows: (1) High DER can reduce PER: If a bank's DER is too high, investors may feel that the bank is borrowing too much and has higher risks. This can cause investors to be less willing to pay a high price for each dollar of profit generated by the bank, resulting in a lower PER. (2) Low DER can increase PER: Conversely, if a bank's DER is low, investors may feel that the bank has lower risk and is more financially stable. This can make investors more willing to pay a higher price for each dollar of profit generated by the bank, resulting in a higher PER. (3) No significant influence: Sometimes, DER may not have a significant influence on PER in banking. This depends on other factors that influence PER, such as profit growth, market factors, and the risks faced by the bank.

Fifteenth, Return On Assets (ROA). In banking, DER can have a significant influence on ROA. The higher the DER of a bank, the greater the risk of bank bankruptcy. Therefore, banks that have high DERs tend to experience difficulties in meeting their debt payment obligations and obtaining new funding. However, on the other hand, DER can also increase a bank's ROA if used effectively. When banks use debt to generate profits that are greater than the interest costs they have to pay, a higher DER can increase ROA. However, this strategy also has higher risks because banks will be more vulnerable to market fluctuations and credit risks. Therefore, it is important for banks to find the right balance between effective

DER and manageable risk to achieve optimal ROA. Banks that are wise in managing their DER can minimize the risk of bankruptcy and maximize their ROA.

Sixteenth, Return On Equity (ROE). In the banking industry, DER can affect ROE because these companies use debt to fund most of their operations. A high DER can cause high interest expenses, thereby reducing the net profit generated by the bank and ultimately affecting ROE. However, low DER can also affect ROE. Banks that use more own capital than debt may not be able to maximize their profit potential because they are too conservative in risk management. Therefore, the optimal DER must be considered carefully to maximize ROE while minimizing risk. In conclusion, DER has a significant influence on ROE in banking companies. Therefore, banking companies need to consider the optimal DER to maximize their ROE without taking unnecessary risks.

Seventeenth, stock returns. In general, the higher the DER of a banking company, the greater the financial risk the company faces. In the short term, a high DER can increase a company's profit potential, because debt interest tends to be lower than the rate of return on equity. However, in the long term, a high DER can pose a risk to the company's financial health, especially if debt interest becomes too high or if the company is unable to generate sufficient profits to pay off its debt. In banking companies, the influence of DER on stock returns can be very complex and depends on various factors. Several factors that can influence the effect of DER on banking company stock returns include: (1) Interest rates: The higher the interest rate, the higher the interest that banking companies must pay on their debt, which in turn can suppress profits and stock returns. However, at the same time, higher interest rates can also increase banking companies' interest margins and increase net profits, which can increase stock returns. (2) Credit quality: Banking companies with high DER tend to have higher credit risk, because they have to pay higher interest and have more debt. If a banking company experiences problems with its credit quality, this can put pressure on profits and stock returns. (3) Business structure: Some banking companies may have a business structure that allows them to utilize higher DERs more effectively. For example, banking companies that have high-quality credit portfolios and many short-term loans may be able to take advantage of higher DERs to increase profits and stock returns. (4) Firm size: Larger banking firms may have more access to capital markets and other funding sources, which may enable them to utilize higher DERs more effectively. In conclusion, DER can have a complex influence on banking company stock returns and its influence depends on various factors that must be taken into account. Therefore, before investing in banking company shares, investors need to carry out an in-depth analysis of the company and see how these factors can influence the effect of DER on stock returns.

Eighteenth, systematic risk. In the banking sector, DER can influence systematic risk, namely risk related to overall market movements. A high DER can increase banking systemic risk because companies rely more on debt as a source of funding. This can make banks more vulnerable to changes in interest rates, monetary policy and adverse economic conditions. On the other hand, a low DER can help reduce banking systemic risk because the company relies more on its own capital. This can make banking more stable and have a tendency to survive in difficult market situations.

Nineteenth, stock price level. __ Several possible influences of DER on stock price levels in banking include: (1) An increase in DER can increase the company's financial risk. The higher the DER, the greater the risk of company bankruptcy because the company has to pay interest and larger debt principal installments. This can reduce investor confidence in the company and reduce share prices. (2) An increase in DER can increase company profits. Companies can use funds obtained from debt to develop their business, such as investing in profitable

projects or expanding markets. This can increase company revenues and profits, which in turn can increase share prices. (3) A high DER can indicate unhealthy financial policies. If a company relies too much on debt to finance its business operations, this can indicate that the company does not have the ability to obtain sufficient capital from internal and external sources. This can lower share prices because investors may perceive the company as a high investment risk. (4) A low DER can indicate that the company has the ability to finance its business operations from internal and external sources. This can increase investor confidence in the company and increase share prices. (5) The effect of DER on Stock Price Level can also be influenced by market conditions and other economic factors. If interest rates are high, a high DER can pose greater financial risks for the company and can reduce share prices. However, if interest rates are low, high DERs can become more attractive due to lower borrowing costs, which can increase share prices.

Twentieth, Yield to Maturity (YTM) bond. In general, the higher a company's DER, the higher the risk of bankruptcy or default risk it has, so the higher the interest rate the company must pay to issue bonds. As a result, the higher the company's DER, the higher the YTM of the bonds it issues. In this case, the relationship between DER and YTM of bonds can be explained as follows: the higher the DER, the greater the risk of corporate default, so investors demand a higher rate of return in return for this risk. Conversely, the lower the DER, the smaller the company's default risk, so investors tend to accept a lower rate of return. However, it is important to note that the relationship between DER and bond YTM is not always linear or in the same direction. There are other factors that also influence bond YTM, such as the company's credit quality, overall financial market conditions, and central bank monetary policy. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze it holistically to understand the influence of DER on the YTM of a company's bonds.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on the mapping of the distribution of journal publications regarding the Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 2009 to 2022 originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 69 published journal articles. Second, based on the VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results regarding the DER ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking are divided into 6 clusters and 196 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 50 topics, cluster 2 consists of 44 topics, cluster 3 consists of 33 topics, cluster 4 consists of 33 topics, cluster 5 consists of 18 topics, and cluster 6 consists of 18 topics. Third, based on mapping literature review studies, there are 20 topics related to the DER ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: bond rating, Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR), expected return, share price, hedging, Islamic Social Reporting (ISR), investor confidence, profit growth, Net Interest Margin (NIM), company value, Murabahah financing, Price to Book Value (PBV), Price Earning Ratio (PER), Return On Assets (ROA), Return On Equity (ROE), stock returns, systematic risk, stock price level, and Yield to Maturity (YTM) bonds.

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